

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF VOLITIONAL REGULATION IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Turdimurodov Dilmurod Yuldashevich

Senior Lecturer, Termez University of Economics and Service

E-mail: profboks2020@gmail.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/my-orcid?orcid=0000-0001-5343-0539>

Annotation: This article analyzes domestic and foreign studies of the formation of volitional regulation and volitional qualities in preschoolers and the factors influencing their formation. Within the framework of the psychology of L. S. Vygotsky, will is understood as the highest mental function, which is formed in vivo as a result of the assimilation of cultural and historical experience in the process of interaction between a child and an adult. This means that the will has a social constructive nature, it is not given to a person initially from birth, but is formed throughout life in the process of solving real life tasks that society first sets before a person, and then he himself.

Key words: will, volitional regulation, volitional competence, executive functions, inhibitory processes, volitionality, self-control.

Introduction. The formation of the will of a preschooler is an extremely attractive topic, on the one hand, because of its very great practical significance, on the other hand, in connection with the age of children. It is customary to form the will at school age, while many authors generally believe that such formation is generally impossible before this age [2].

Scientists considered the will as the mastery of one's own behavior, which becomes possible thanks to the invention and use of signs - artificial "means of behavior". The development of a child's will begins with the acquisition of the ability to control their movements, which takes place in the environment of adults and under their guidance [3, 4]. The development of the will begins in early

childhood and goes a long way (the emergence of actions aimed at the fulfillment of desire; selective actions; readiness to act contrary to immediate emotional prompting; understanding of the "rules" of behavior).

By the end of preschool - the beginning of school age, the child is already consciously trying to set a task for himself and purposefully fulfill it. Gradually, as a result of training and education on the basis of involuntary attention, memory, impulsive actions, higher mental functions are formed - voluntary attention, memory, purposeful thinking, voluntary actions [1, 4, 6].

Willpower is a psychosocial quality associated with autonomy, thanks to which the child learns to make free choices and limit himself [6, 7, 8, 9].

Some authors argue that there is no willpower "in general", manifested equally in all situations. The same person, when meeting with various difficulties, behaves differently: in some situations he shows great willpower, in others - insignificant. Some are more successful in overcoming fatigue (that is, they show greater patience), but cannot so successfully overcome the fear that arises. Others cope well with fear, but are unable to resist the feeling of boredom and quit monotonous work [10, 11]. And therefore, manifestations of the will are always specific and conditioned by those difficulties (with all their inherent features) that a person overcomes [12, 13].

Volitional effort is a mental stress that mobilizes a person's internal resources in order to overcome obstacles [6, 9, 11, 14].

Volitional qualities are qualities that are manifested in a person's volitional actions and are characterized by perseverance, determination, endurance, courage [6, 8, 12, 15].

The difficulty of measuring volitional qualities lies in the fact that the researcher must control: the strength of the need, the intensity of the experienced emotion (which can either weaken or strengthen the energy of volitional action), as well as the actual volitional effort of a person. Volitional regulation - mental processes carried out using a person's own activity [16, 17].

There are the following strategies for the formation of volitional regulation [12, 16, 19]: The first strategy can be called willpower training. She suggests that willpower can be trained in the same way as a skeletal muscle, that is, with the help of various exercises, for example, holding the breath or holding weights [5, 7]. However, empirical studies show that, firstly, the effectiveness of volitional regulation is not always proportional to the amount of effort expended, and secondly, the ability for volitional effort in some types of activity is usually not associated with the ability for volitional effort in other types of activity [18, 19]. The second strategy - the education of volitional qualities - is based on the idea that the manifestations of volitional regulation are always specific. This approach is most widely used in sports psychology. It was believed that athletes of different profiles form a different set of volitional qualities. So, in a stayer, the most developed qualities are perseverance and perseverance, and in a gymnast, endurance and self-control [21].

The third strategy - the formation of a person's volitional competence - is based on ideas about the systemic structure of volitional regulation, which is the result of the combined work of various mental processes and functions. Studies show that, unlike volitional qualities, volitional regulation strategies can be used to solve a wide range of problems, since they are not aimed at managing specific types of activity, but at mastering mental processes and functions [20].

Thus, the main pedagogical task of educating the will should be to master the means and strategies of volitional regulation or, in other words, to form the volitional competence of the individual [22].

Longitudinal studies have shown that preschoolers who are able to delay receiving rewards, that is, who have more effective volitional regulation, after 12 years had better control over themselves in difficult situations, were less tempted, were less distracted in conditions that required concentration, had more developed intelligence, relied more on their strength and trust their judgment. They were more resistant to various stress factors. And at the age of 25-30, they were better

able to pursue long-term goals and achieve them. They had a higher level of education, learned new information more intensively and quickly transformed it into practical skills, which means they better adapted to new conditions and activities.

It has been experimentally shown that the emotional-volitional component of the psychological readiness of children for school consists of two components and has indicators and criteria. Indicators include controlled, conscious, controlled, emotionally restrained behavior. The criteria for the formation of the emotional-volitional component are the ability to listen, fulfill requirements, act according to the rules.

It was found that positive emotions have a more positive effect on volitional regulation, contribute to the experience of positive emotions when exerting effort, and increase motivation for learning. Negative emotions make it difficult for preschoolers to form the volitional efforts necessary for schooling. Volitional readiness is considered formed if the older preschooler has mastered such a structure of activity and behavior in which a goal is motivated, efforts are made and one's own activity is regulated towards achieving the goal.

The criterion of moral orientation makes a radical correction in the assessment of the volitional properties of the personality: developed purposefulness, perseverance, endurance, courage will in some cases be presented to us as the highest positive values of the personality, and in others - as the most negative properties (if they serve the lowest motives and needs) .

Independence is the desire and ability to carry out any activity without outside help. It manifests itself in independent decision-making, the implementation of the planned, self-control, in taking responsibility for deeds and actions. Independence as a strong-willed personality trait is already inherent in preschoolers.

When a child chooses among a certain number of materials what he likes, he goes to the locker, takes the item to his table or agrees to give it to his friend; when

he waits for a classmate to release material that is interesting to him; when he diligently and attentively repeats the same exercise, correcting the error suggested by the material itself; when, in exercises in silence, he restrains all his impulses, all movements, then, rising on a signal, he moves extremely carefully so as not to stomp, not to knock chairs, the child performs many volitional actions. We can say that there is a training of his will.

The curriculum of the Montessori system does not mention executive functions, but what M. Montessori means by "normalization" includes the presence of formed executive functions.

Normalization is the transition from disorder, impulsiveness, and inattention to self-discipline, independence, orderliness, and peacefulness. Also, the results of the study by K. Rathunde showed that the students of the Montessori school felt more active, relaxed, sociable, felt the importance of the work performed, compared with students of traditional schools. They were interested in what they were doing. They felt the support of teachers, worked in a spirit of cooperation and independence, that is, they experienced a state of flow - an optimal experience when the load on the child corresponds to his capabilities.

Conclusions. Volitional regulation is the result of the combined work of various mental processes and functions. The preschool period is a sensitive period for the formation of volitional regulation, and its formation affects the quality of all future life. There are many factors that influence the development of volitional regulation and volitional qualities. The family plays an important role in the development of strong-willed qualities. The possibility of freedom of choice predetermines the development of such volitional qualities as independence, initiative, discipline, organization, and a state of concentration.

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